

Original article

Influence of Lactation on the Biochemical Parameters of Blood in Donkey

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Abstract

The biochemical parameters of the blood give us clues about the health of the animals. In the animals studied, the biochemical parameters fall within the normal limits. The biochemical parameters of the blood are influenced by lactation as follows: ALT (U/L), has the highest average values in lactation 2 (14.18 ± 0.55 U/L), and in lactation 4 (15.71 ± 0.21 U/L). AST (U/L) in lactation I showed the lowest values, 244 ± 5.01 (U/L) and 256.28 ± 2.85 (U/L) in lactation IV. Total protein (g/L) varied in the range 61.28 ± 3.36 (g/L) lactation I and lactation IV, 67.86 ± 1.96 (g/L). Total bilirubin (mmol/L), in lactation I is 7.33 ± 0.57 (mmol/L) and in IV lactation 8.61 ± 0.43 (mmol/L). Magnesium behaves similar to total bilirubin having the lowest values in lactation I, 0.72 ± 0.05 (mmol/L) and 0.83 ± 0.04 (mmol/L) in lactation IV.

Keywords: donkey, albumin, Mg, ALT, AST, CK.

1. Introduction

In the zootechnical field, the monitoring of the health status of animals and diseases is of major importance. Lately there has been an increasing concern about the health and welfare of animals. The aim is to increase the milk production through the correct management of the conditions and procedures of the farms, especially those that can cause suffering in animals [5]. Knowing the biomarkers in the blood represents a breakthrough in the development of work programs and nutritional programs in the farms of donkeys and greatly helps the possibility of preserving the donkeys, a species that until now has been neglected in our country.

Metabolic stress and feeding influence animal fertility [1]. Factors that influence the biochemical profile of donkeys, cows, and buffaloes are: feeding, reproduction, season, lactation, parturition, maintenance mode and animal health [1, 14].

Within the farms it should be kept in mind that the economic losses caused by the nutritional changes can cause hematological and biochemical changes. In order to avoid various metabolic and morphopathological changes, certain preventive measures are necessary through the use of a correct diet. The aim of this study was to analyze the biochemical parameters of the blood in the donkey depending on the lactation.

2. Material and Method

To determine the biochemical parameters, the blood, immediately after harvesting, was subjected to centrifugation in order to separate the serum.

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After centrifugation and separation of the serum, the samples were immediately frozen in Eppendorf. Determinations for biochemistry were performed using the semi-automatic reagent screen point biochemistry analyzer.

It is a general purpose photometer, controlled by a macroprocessor, with 6 filters and 37°C incubation block.

The biochemical parameters analyzed are:

- urea;
- total protein;
- glucose;
- albumin;
- creatinine;
- cholesterol;
- potassium;
- triglycerides;
- total calcium;

- sodium;
- total bilirubin;
- magnesium;
- ALT - alaninaminotransferase;
- AST - aspartataminotransferase;
- ALP-alkaline phosphatase;
- GGT - gamma glutamyltransferase;
- CK- creatinine kinase.

3. Results and Discussions

Tables 1 and 2 show the biochemical parameters of donkey blood for lactates I-IV. Creatinine ($\mu\text{mol/L}$) shows changes depending on the lactation as follows: in lactation 1 the values for creatinine are the lowest of 102.22 ± 4.64 ($\mu\text{mol/L}$) and it increases reaching the highest values in lactation 4, of 133.48 ± 4.90 ($\mu\text{mol/L}$).

Table 1. Mean values and variability for biochemical parameters of donkey blood for lactation I and II

Parameter	Lactation I (n=15)		Lactation II (n=15)	
	X \pm sx	V%	X \pm sx	V%
Urea (mmol/L)	5.90 \pm 0.84	31.72	6.04 \pm 0.49	18.04
Total protein (g/L)	61.28 \pm 3.36	12.27	66.40 \pm 3.02	10.17
Glucose (mmol/L)	4.65 \pm 0.42	20.09	5.13 \pm 0.50	21.81
Albumin (g/L)	24.96 \pm 1.39	12.42	24.48 \pm 0.89	8.09
Creatinine ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	102.22 \pm 4.64	10.15	110.56 \pm 4.42	8.93
Cholesterol (mmol/L)	1.74 \pm 0.16	19.97	1.98 \pm 0.07	7.84
K (mmol/L)	3.87 \pm 0.12	6.73	4.10 \pm 0.23	12.61
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	0.66 \pm 0.08	26.61	0.67 \pm 0.09	30.78
Total calcium (mmol/L)	3.08 \pm 0.14	10.15	2.95 \pm 0.22	16.64
Na (mmol/L)	124.40 \pm 5.81	10.44	118.35 \pm 3.21	6.07
Total bilirubin (mmol/L)	7.33 \pm 0.57	17.42	8.10 \pm 0.66	18.19
Mg (mmol/L)	0.72 \pm 0.05	15.65	0.76 \pm 0.04	12.97
ALT (U/L)	12.97 \pm 0.90	15.43	14.18 \pm 0.55	8.62
AST (U/L)	244 \pm 5.01	4.59	270.04 \pm 7.95	6.58
ALP (U/L)	199.24 \pm 5.74	6.44	209.22 \pm 7.57	8.09
GGT (U/L)	58.74 \pm 3.76	14.3	76.34 \pm 2.10	6.15
CK (U/L)	166.76 \pm 3.97	5.33	199.02 \pm 3.58	4.02

V- variability; X - average value; n - the number of blood samples.

Table 2. Mean values and variability for biochemical parameters of donkey blood for lactation III and IV

Parameter	Lactation III (n=15)		Lactation IV (n=15)	
	X±sx	V%	X±sx	V%
Urea (mmol/L)	7.62±0.60	17.47	7.71±0.64	18.62
Total protein (g/L)	65.42±1.93	6.61	67.86±1.96	6.45
Glucose (mmol/L)	5.20±0.23	9.75	6.19±0.30	10.78
Albumin (g/L)	24.64±1.05	9.51	25.22±1.06	9.41
Creatinine (µmol/L)	114.56±5.98	11.67	133.48±4.90	8.21
Cholesterol (mmol/L)	1.55±0.14	19.44	1.84±0.14	17.41
K (mmol/L)	4.37±0.25	12.56	4.76±0.17	8.02
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	0.64±0.09	30.30	0.85±0.09	22.74
Total calcium(mmol/L)	2.88±0.08	6.60	2.93±0.09	6.77
Na (mmol/L)	126.16±3.65	6.47	122.86±3.25	5.91
Total bilirubin (mmol/L)	8.49±0.56	14.85	8.61±0.43	11.29
Mg (mmol/L)	0.77±0.07	19.52	0.83±0.04	10.37
ALT (U/L)	12.86±0.88	15.24	15.71±0.21	2.97
AST (U/L)	272.54±4.68	3.84	256.28±2.85	2.49
ALP (U/L)	215.20±2.43	2.52	226.32±4.73	4.67
GGT (U/L)	77.10±1.53	4.43	81.78± 4.34	11.87
CK (U/L)	205±3.74	4.08	212±4.85	5.1

V- variability; X - average value; n - the number of blood samples.

Creatinine shows higher values in males in the study reported by [4, 6]. ALT (U/L) varied between 12.97 ± 0.90 in lactation I and 15.71 ± 0.21 in lactation IV. ALP, GGT, CK also behave according to lactation. This aspect may also be influenced by muscle tissue which is larger compared to females. GGT (U/L) shows an average value in lactation 1 of 58.74 ± 3.76 (U/L) and 81.78 ± 4.34 (U/L) in lactation 4 (Tables 1 and 2). Lactation influences albumin and total protein, showing the lowest values in the first three lactations and the highest values in lactation 4. There are several factors that can influence the biochemical parameters of the blood and the hematological indices even within the same species, namely: notional factors, aspects of the area of provenance, mode of operation, sex, age, lactation [6, 9, 10, 11, 13]. The biochemical profile in donkeys is significantly influenced by sex, age, muscle mass, nutrition, physiological status and health of donkey [7, 9, 15]. Carrying out studies on blood biomarkers, hematological and biochemical parameters provides important information on donkeys and can

be used as indicators of the health status of these animals [2, 8, 12].

4. Conclusions

The biochemical parameters of the blood are significantly influenced by lactation. The average values obtained for these parameters are in the normal values. Lactations I and II have the lowest values and they increase with the number of lactations. It can be concluded that lactation changes these parameters. It is very important to analyze the biochemical profile of blood in the donkey, because it provides us with important information about the health of the animal.

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